

Applying Masked Language Modeling to Enhance Song Lyrics Prediction in the LyrAics ERC Project

Adrián Ghajari, Pedro Hernández, Alejandro Benito-Santos, Salvador Ros, Victor Fresno, Elena González-Blanco

Abstract

Language models, particularly large-scale transformer models, have significantly advanced the state-of-the-art in various natural language processing tasks. Among their most notable features is transfer learning, which allows models pre-trained on generic data to be fine-tuned for specific tasks, yielding competitive results with reduced computational costs. Transfer learning works under the assumption that both training and test data share the same distribution and similar joint probability distributions, which is not always the case. Domain adaptation, a sub-field of machine learning where models are further trained on task-specific data, has also demonstrated improvements in several aspects of the performance of language models. In this paper, we present the LyrAics project, which aims to improve song recommendations by leveraging unsupervised domain adaptation of pre-trained language models. Song lyrics, characterized by their deviation from grammatical norms and emotive nature, present unique challenges for natural language understanding. This work investigates the techniques and process of unsupervised domain adaptation.

Keywords: Language models, transfer learning, domain adaptation, song recommendations.